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CONTACTS

Phone: **+998 50 737 87 88**

Website: <https://ist-journal.uz>

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SOCIOLINGUISTIC FEATURES OF NEGATIVE AESTHETIC EVALUATION UNITS DENOTING PHYSICAL APPEARANCE IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

Qalandarova Shaxzoda Qurbonboy qizi

E-mail: shaxzoda.qalandarova.96@gmail.com

Trainee Teacher

Uzbekistan State World Languages University

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Abstract. This article examines the sociolinguistic features of negative aesthetic evaluation units denoting physical appearance in English and Uzbek. The research focuses on lexical and phraseological units belonging to the semantic field of “ugliness”, including English units such as *ugly*, *unattractive*, *plain*, *hideous* and *repulsive*, as well as Uzbek units such as *xunuk*, *ko‘rimsiz*, *badbashara*, *sovuq* and *yoqimsiz*. The aim of the study is to reveal how these units function in speech under the influence of social factors such as age, gender, politeness, communicative situation and cultural norms. The analysis shows that negative aesthetic evaluation is not limited to the description of appearance; it also reflects social attitudes, emotional distance, cultural etiquette and evaluative stereotypes. In both languages, direct nomination may sound rude, while indirect or softened expressions are used to reduce communicative tension. The findings contribute to comparative semantics, sociolinguistics, intercultural communication and the study of evaluative vocabulary in language use.

Key words: negative aesthetic evaluation, physical appearance, ugliness, semantic field, sociolinguistics, gender, politeness, English and Uzbek.

Аннотация. В статье исследуются социолингвистические особенности единиц отрицательной эстетической оценки, обозначающих внешность, в английском и узбекском языках. Основное внимание уделяется лексическим и фразеологическим единицам функционально-семантического поля «некрасивость», включая английские единицы *ugly*, *unattractive*, *plain*, *hideous*, *repulsive* и узбекские единицы *xunuk*, *ko‘rimsiz*, *badbashara*, *sovuq*, *yoqimsiz*. Цель исследования заключается в выявлении того, как данные единицы функционируют в речи под влиянием возраста, пола, коммуникативной ситуации, речевого этикета и культурных норм. Анализ показывает, что отрицательная эстетическая оценка не ограничивается описанием внешности, а отражает социальные отношения, эмоциональную дистанцию, культурную вежливость и оценочные стереотипы. В узбекском языке подобные оценки часто связаны с нормами такта, сдержанности и косвенной характеристики, тогда как в английском языке важную роль играют политкорректность и стратегии смягчения. В обоих языках прямое наименование может восприниматься как грубое, поэтому смягченные и косвенные выражения используются для снижения коммуникативного напряжения и сохранения лица собеседника. Результаты исследования имеют значение для сопоставительной семантики, социолингвистики и межкультурной коммуникации в современном сопоставительном языкознании.

Ключевые слова: отрицательная эстетическая оценка, внешность, некрасивость, семантическое поле, социолингвистика, гендер, речевой этикет, английский и узбекский языки.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada ingliz va o‘zbek tillarida tashqi ko‘rinishni ifodalovchi salbiy estetik baho birliklarining sotsiolingvistik xususiyatlari tadqiq etiladi. Tadqiqot “xunuklik” funksional-semantik maydoniga mansub leksik va frazeologik birliklarga, jumladan ingliz tilidagi *ugly*, *unattractive*, *plain*, *hideous*, *repulsive* hamda o‘zbek tilidagi *xunuk*, *ko‘rimsiz*, *badbashara*, *sovuq*, *yoqimsiz* kabi birliklarga qaratilgan. Maqolaning maqsadi ushbu birliklarning yosh, jins, nutqiy vaziyat, muloqot odobi va madaniy me‘yorlar ta‘sirida qanday qo‘llanishini aniqlashdan iborat. Tahlil shuni ko‘rsatadiki, salbiy estetik baho faqat tashqi ko‘rinishni tasvirlash bilan cheklanmaydi, balki ijtimoiy munosabat, emotsional masofa, madaniy odob va baholovchi stereotiplarni ham aks ettiradi. O‘zbek tilida bunday birliklar ko‘pincha odob, andisha va bilvosita baholash bilan bog‘liq bo‘lsa, ingliz tilida siyosiy korrektilik va yumshoq ifodalash strategiyalari muhim o‘rin tutadi. Har ikki tilda to‘g‘ridan-to‘g‘ri nomlash qo‘pol eshitilishi mumkin. Shu bois yumshatilgan ifodalar kommunikativ keskinlikni kamaytiradi va suhbatdosh sha‘nini saqlashga xizmat qiladi. Natijalar qiyosiy semantika, sotsiolingvistika va madaniyatlararo muloqot tadqiqotlari uchun dolzarb ilmiy-nazariy va amaliy ahamiyatga ega ekanligini ko‘rsatadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: salbiy estetik baho, tashqi ko‘rinish, xunuklik, semantik maydon, sotsiolingvistika, gender, nutqiy odob, ingliz va o‘zbek tillari.

INTRODUCTION

Language is not only a means of naming objects and phenomena, but also an important instrument for expressing social attitudes, emotions, values and cultural norms. In everyday communication, speakers constantly evaluate people, objects and situations. One of the most sensitive types of evaluation is related to physical appearance, because it directly concerns an individual's identity, dignity and social image. For this reason, negative aesthetic evaluation units denoting physical appearance require not only semantic, but also sociolinguistic analysis.

The semantic field of "ugliness" includes words and expressions that describe a person or object as aesthetically unpleasant, unattractive or socially undesirable. In English, this field may include such units as *ugly*, *unattractive*, *plain*, *hideous*, *repulsive* and *unpleasant-looking*. In Uzbek, similar meanings are expressed through the words *xunuk*, *ko'rimsiz*, *badbashara*, *sovuq*, *yoqimsiz* and *beo'xshov*. However, these words are not used in the same way in all contexts. Their choice depends on the speaker's intention, the relationship between interlocutors, gender expectations, age, cultural norms and the degree of politeness required in a particular communicative situation.

Sociolinguistics studies the relationship between language and society. According to Labov, linguistic variation is closely connected with social factors, and speech forms cannot be fully understood without considering the social environment in which they are used (Labov, 1972). This idea is especially relevant to the study of evaluative vocabulary, because evaluation is always socially marked. When a speaker calls someone *ugly* or *xunuk*, the word does not merely describe appearance; it also expresses attitude, emotional distance and, in some cases, social judgment.

The relevance of the present study is determined by the fact that negative aesthetic evaluation units in English and Uzbek have not only lexical meanings, but also strong sociocultural implications. In Uzbek communication, direct negative evaluation of a person's appearance is often considered impolite and may contradict the norms of *andisha*, respect and indirectness. In English, especially in modern public discourse, direct evaluation of appearance may be avoided due to politeness, sensitivity and politically correct communication. Therefore, the comparative study of such units helps reveal how language reflects cultural values and social norms.

The aim of this article is to analyze the sociolinguistic features of negative aesthetic evaluation units denoting physical appearance in English and Uzbek. The object of the research is the lexical and phraseological units belonging to the semantic field of "ugliness" in the two languages. The subject of the research is their semantic, pragmatic and sociolinguistic functioning in different communicative contexts. The study uses descriptive, comparative, semantic and sociolinguistic methods.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The theoretical basis of this research is connected with studies in semantics, sociolinguistics, pragmatics and gender linguistics. The concept of the semantic field is important for understanding how words are grouped around a common meaning. Lyons states that lexical meaning is not isolated, but exists in relation to other meanings within a system (Lyons, 1977). From this point of view, the words *ugly*, *unattractive*, *hideous* and *repulsive* belong to one semantic field, but they differ in intensity, emotional colouring and stylistic use. Similarly, Uzbek words such as *xunuk*, *ko'rimsiz*, *badbashara* and *yoqimsiz* form a semantic group, but each of them has its own pragmatic and expressive features.

Cruse emphasizes that lexical units may differ not only in denotative meaning, but also in expressive, stylistic and contextual value (Cruse, 1986). This is significant for the analysis of negative aesthetic evaluation, because the difference between *unattractive* and *hideous* is not only semantic, but also emotional. *Unattractive* may sound relatively neutral or polite, while *hideous* expresses a much stronger negative reaction. In Uzbek, *ko'rimsiz* is usually milder than *badbashara*, which has a more offensive and emotionally marked character.

Sociolinguistic theory allows us to examine how social factors influence the use of language. Trudgill notes that language varies according to social class, gender, age and context (Trudgill, 2000). Holmes also points out that speakers choose different linguistic forms depending on the social relationship between participants and the communicative setting (Holmes, 2013). Therefore, the use of words denoting ugliness may vary in formal and informal speech, among young and older speakers, as well as in private conversation and public discourse.

The issue of politeness is also central to this topic. Brown and Levinson's theory of politeness explains how speakers try to protect their own and others' "face" in communication (Brown & Levinson, 1987). Negative comments about appearance are potentially face-threatening acts because they can hurt the addressee's dignity. For this reason, speakers often use indirect expressions, euphemisms or softened forms instead of direct negative nominations. For example, in English one may say *not very attractive* instead of *ugly*. In Uzbek, one may say *unchalik ko'rkam emas* instead of *xunuk*.

Gender linguistics is another important perspective. Lakoff argues that women's speech is often socially expected to be more polite, indirect and emotionally controlled (Lakoff, 1975). Although this view has been developed and criticized by later researchers, it remains useful for understanding how gender expectations influence evaluative language. Eckert and McConnell-Ginet emphasize that gender is not simply a biological category, but a social practice reflected in language use (Eckert & McConnell-Ginet, 2013). In the case of negative aesthetic evaluation, women are often evaluated more frequently through appearance-related vocabulary than men, which reflects gender stereotypes existing in society.

Cultural semantics also contributes to the analysis. Wierzbicka states that words reflect the cultural values and communicative norms of a speech community (Wierzbicka, 1997). This idea is important for comparing English and Uzbek units of negative aesthetic evaluation. In Uzbek culture, indirectness, respect for the interlocutor and avoidance of open insult are highly valued in many communicative situations. Therefore, the direct use of *xunuk* or *badbashara* may be perceived as rude, especially in relation to a person. In English-speaking contexts, direct negative evaluation of appearance may also be avoided, but the reasons are often connected with politeness, social sensitivity and modern norms of non-discriminatory communication.

The explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language provides the lexical meanings of such words as *xunuk*, *ko'rimsiz*, *badbashara* and *yoqimsiz*, showing their relation to unpleasant appearance, lack of beauty or negative impression (Madvaliyev, 2006–2008). However, dictionary meanings alone are not sufficient to explain how these words function in real communication. Their use depends on social context, emotional intention and cultural acceptability. Therefore, this study combines semantic and sociolinguistic approaches.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research is based on qualitative linguistic analysis. The main materials of the study are lexical and phraseological units denoting negative aesthetic evaluation of physical appearance in English and Uzbek. The English materials include *ugly*, *unattractive*, *plain*, *hideous*, *repulsive*, *unpleasant-looking* and *awkward-looking*. The Uzbek materials include *xunuk*, *ko'rimsiz*, *badbashara*, *sovuq*, *yoqimsiz*, *beo'xshov* and *aft-angori yoqimsiz*. These units were selected because they represent different degrees of negative evaluation and various stylistic levels.

The first method used in the article is semantic analysis. It helps identify the denotative and connotative meanings of the selected units. For example, *ugly* and *hideous* both express negative evaluation, but *hideous* has a stronger emotional meaning. In Uzbek, *xunuk* expresses a general negative evaluation, while *badbashara* is more expressive and offensive.

The second method is comparative analysis. It is used to identify similarities and differences between English and Uzbek units. Both languages have direct and indirect ways of expressing negative aesthetic evaluation. However, the cultural conditions of their use differ. English often relies on softened adjectives and polite phrases, while Uzbek frequently uses indirectness, contextual implication and culturally marked expressions.

The third method is sociolinguistic analysis. It examines the role of age, gender, social distance, politeness and communicative situation. The same word may function differently depending on who says it, to whom it is addressed, where it is used and for what purpose. For instance, a word used jokingly among close friends may be considered offensive in formal communication.

The fourth method is contextual analysis. Negative aesthetic evaluation units are interpreted not as isolated dictionary items, but as elements of discourse. Their meaning changes according to context. In a literary text, *hideous* may create expressive imagery; in everyday speech, it may sound insulting. In Uzbek, *sovuq* may literally mean "cold", but when used to describe appearance, it can indicate an unpleasant or unattractive impression.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The analysis shows that negative aesthetic evaluation units denoting physical appearance in English and Uzbek may be divided into several groups according to intensity, stylistic colouring and sociolinguistic function.

The first group consists of neutral or relatively mild units. In English, *unattractive* and *plain* are less offensive than *ugly*. The word *plain* often refers to a person who is not beautiful, but not necessarily unpleasant in appearance. It may be used in a softer way, especially in descriptive or literary contexts. In Uzbek, *ko'rimsiz* can function as a milder equivalent. It expresses a lack of attractiveness without necessarily carrying a strong insult. For example, *ko'rimsiz odam* is negative, but it is usually less aggressive than *badbashara odam*.

The second group includes direct negative units. In English, *ugly* is the central lexical unit of this semantic field. It directly expresses the idea of physical unattractiveness. In Uzbek, *xunuk* performs a similar function.

Both words are semantically direct and socially sensitive. Their use in relation to a person can be face-threatening, especially if the person is present or if the speech situation requires politeness. This confirms Brown and Levinson's idea that direct negative evaluation may threaten the social image of the addressee (Brown & Levinson, 1987).

The third group includes highly expressive and emotionally strong units. English words such as *hideous* and *repulsive* express a stronger negative reaction than *ugly*. They may imply not only unattractiveness, but also disgust or rejection. Uzbek words such as *badbashara* and *afti yoqimsiz* may have a similar expressive force. These words are more offensive and are usually used in emotionally charged speech, conflict situations or expressive literary description.

The fourth group includes indirect or metaphorical units. In Uzbek, *sovuq* may be used to describe a person's unpleasant appearance or impression. The word does not directly mean "ugly", but in context it may express aesthetic and emotional distance. English also uses indirect expressions such as *not good-looking*, *not very attractive* and *unpleasant-looking*. Such forms soften the negative meaning and reduce the risk of open insult.

The findings also show that gender plays an important role in the use of these units. In many societies, women are more frequently evaluated through appearance-related language than men. This reflects broader cultural stereotypes about beauty, femininity and social value. As Eckert and McConnell-Ginet note, gender is reproduced through everyday linguistic practices (Eckert & McConnell-Ginet, 2013). In English, phrases such as *plain woman* or *unattractive girl* may carry social judgments that go beyond physical description. In Uzbek, negative evaluation of a woman's appearance may be especially sensitive because it can be connected with cultural ideas about beauty, marriageability and social reputation.

Age is another important factor. Younger speakers may use direct or slang-like expressions more freely, especially in informal communication and social media. Older speakers, particularly in Uzbek communicative culture, may prefer indirect forms because of respect, etiquette and social restraint. For example, instead of saying *u xunuk*, a speaker may say *ko'rinishi unchalik emas* or *unchalik ko'rkam emas*. In English, similar softening can be observed in expressions such as *not particularly attractive* or *not the best-looking*.

Social distance also influences word choice. Among close friends, negative aesthetic evaluation may sometimes be used jokingly. However, in formal or distant relationships, direct words such as *ugly* and *xunuk* are generally avoided. This supports Holmes's idea that speech forms are selected according to the relationship between interlocutors and the social context of communication (Holmes, 2013).

The comparative analysis of English and Uzbek shows that both languages possess a rich set of units for expressing negative aesthetic evaluation. However, the sociolinguistic use of these units differs according to cultural norms and communicative expectations.

In English, the semantic field of "ugliness" has a clear scale of intensity. The word *unattractive* is relatively neutral and polite. *Plain* may be mild and context-dependent. *Ugly* is direct and potentially offensive. *Hideous* and *repulsive* are emotionally strong and often express disgust. This gradation shows that English speakers can choose from different levels of negative evaluation depending on the situation.

In Uzbek, the semantic field also contains degrees of intensity. *Ko'rimsiz* is comparatively mild, *xunuk* is direct, *badbashara* is strongly negative and rude, *sovuq* is indirect and metaphorical, while *yoqimsiz* may refer to both appearance and general impression. The Uzbek system shows a strong interaction between semantic meaning and cultural etiquette. Direct negative evaluation of someone's appearance may be considered not only impolite, but also morally inappropriate in many situations.

One of the main differences between English and Uzbek is the cultural mechanism of softening. In English, softening is often achieved through grammatical and lexical means such as *not very*, *rather*, *a little* and *not particularly*. For example, *She is not very attractive* sounds less direct than *She is ugly*. In Uzbek, softening may be achieved through indirectness, understatement and contextual implication: *ko'rinishi unchalik emas*, *unchalik ko'rkam emas*, *aftidan biroz sovuqroq*. These expressions reduce the emotional sharpness of the evaluation.

Another difference is connected with cultural values. Uzbek communication is often influenced by the norms of respect, modesty and *andisha*. These norms encourage speakers to avoid direct criticism, especially regarding personal appearance. English communication also values politeness, but in contemporary discourse there is an additional tendency to avoid appearance-based judgment because it may be considered discriminatory, insensitive or socially inappropriate. Therefore, both languages avoid direct insult, although the cultural motivations may differ.

The analysis also reveals that negative aesthetic evaluation units may function as markers of social power. A person who negatively evaluates another person's appearance may position themselves as superior or judgmental. This is especially visible in gendered discourse, where women's appearance is often evaluated more strictly. Lakoff's observations about gendered expectations in language remain relevant in this regard,

because women are often socially expected to be both polite speakers and objects of aesthetic evaluation (Lakoff, 1975). Thus, words denoting ugliness may reinforce existing social stereotypes.

From a pragmatic point of view, such units perform several functions. First, they describe appearance. Second, they express an emotional reaction. Third, they mark social distance. Fourth, they may insult, criticize or humiliate. Fifth, in literary or media discourse, they may create expressive imagery. Therefore, these units should not be treated only as adjectives of appearance. They are evaluative signs that connect language, emotion and society.

The semantic and sociolinguistic comparison also shows that the concept of ugliness is culturally relative. What is considered unattractive in one culture may not have the same meaning in another. Wierzbicka's idea that words reflect cultural models is important here (Wierzbicka, 1997). The words *ugly* and *xunuk* may appear to be direct equivalents, but their actual use is shaped by different communicative traditions. Therefore, in translation, literal equivalence is not always sufficient. The translator must consider intensity, politeness, context and cultural acceptability.

The results of the study have practical importance for comparative linguistics, translation studies and language teaching. Learners of English and Uzbek should understand not only dictionary meanings, but also pragmatic restrictions. For instance, translating *badbashara* simply as *ugly* may not always convey the same emotional strength. In some contexts, *hideous* or *repulsive* may be closer. Conversely, translating *plain* as *xunuk* may be too strong; *ko'rimsiz* or *unchalik chiroyli emas* may be more appropriate.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The analysis of negative aesthetic evaluation units denoting physical appearance in English and Uzbek demonstrates that these units represent a complex semantic and sociolinguistic phenomenon. They do not merely describe external appearance, but also express social attitudes, emotional distance, cultural norms and communicative intentions.

In both languages, the semantic field of "ugliness" includes different degrees of intensity. English uses such units as *unattractive*, *plain*, *ugly*, *hideous* and *repulsive*, while Uzbek uses *ko'rimsiz*, *xunuk*, *badbashara*, *sovuq* and *yoqimsiz*. These units differ in emotional force, stylistic colouring and pragmatic effect.

The study shows that direct negative evaluation, such as *ugly* or *xunuk*, may be perceived as rude or offensive. For this reason, speakers often use softened or indirect expressions. In English, this is achieved through forms such as *not very attractive* or *not particularly good-looking*. In Uzbek, indirect expressions such as *ko'rinishi unchalik emas* or *unchalik ko'rkam emas* are more acceptable in polite communication.

Sociolinguistic factors such as gender, age, social distance and communicative situation strongly influence the choice of these units. Women are more frequently evaluated through appearance-related language, which reflects broader gender stereotypes. Younger speakers may use direct forms more freely, while older speakers often prefer indirect and polite expressions.

The comparison also proves that English and Uzbek units of negative aesthetic evaluation are not always fully equivalent. Their meanings are shaped by cultural values and communicative norms. Therefore, the study of such units is important for comparative semantics, sociolinguistics, intercultural communication and translation practice.

In conclusion, negative aesthetic evaluation units denoting physical appearance should be analyzed as linguistic, social and cultural signs. Their use reveals how speakers evaluate others, manage politeness, express emotions and reproduce social norms through language.

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